

D4.2

Dissemination and Communication Final Report

AUSTRALO

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D4.2

Dissemination and Communication Final Report

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Abstract

This document provides a comprehensive overview of all dissemination and communication actions undertaken to reach a critical mass throughout EU4CHILD's lifetime. It contains a detailed description of the project's visual identity, online channels, promotional materials and publications, together with an introduction to its fieldwork methodology.

Keywords

Communication, Dissemination, Outreach, Impact, Engagement, Promotion, Consultation

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Nature of the deliverable

R

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

✓

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

CO Confidential to EU4CHILD project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DoA	Description of Action
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable intends to act as an update and in-depth review of EU4CHILD's strategy and framework conceived for **Communication, Dissemination and Engagement** purposes.

The initial design of this framework was previously outlined in EU4CHILD's **Impact Master Plan** (D4.1), during the early stages of the project. Now comes the time to reflect on the outreach efforts carried out through the project and study its overall performance.

Thus, the present document provides a comprehensive recap of the Communication and Dissemination timeline, tools and methodology, together with detailed descriptions of every action that has been put in place to:

- Effectively **promote the project and its results** in any public forum (e.g. events, conferences, webinars...), either on a participant role or as hosts.
- Accurately **disseminate the results available**, both to the scientific communities within our clinical and technical spheres and the general public, making EU4CHILD's achievements easily understood and widely accessible to a non-expert audience.
- Maintain **dedicated communication channels** that are open, active and engaging in the way they inform and educate about the project: keeping our target audiences up to date on our ambition, work plan and EU4CHILD's day-to-day.
- Design and execute a methodology to support and guide EU4CHILD's **fieldwork** efforts, in the form of a **stakeholder consultation** (e.g. focus groups, interviews, surveys) with children and adolescents with Childhood Cancer, survivors, family and caregivers, healthcare professionals, healthcare providers, policy and decision makers, IT experts and other related EU-funded initiatives.

In keeping with these high-level goals, this deliverable has been structured as follows:

- **Section 1** is the **Introduction**, where the purpose and scope of the document are outlined.
- **Section 2** is concerned with the **Dissemination & Communication strategy**, where a bird's eye view of the outreach timeline and performance is presented.
- **Section 3** explains the **Communication & Dissemination activities implemented**, where more details are given on specific actions, highlights and metrics.
- **Section 4** details the **Fieldwork overview**, where all efforts regarding stakeholder consultation are presented.
- **Section 5** outlines the **Conclusions** of this deliverable.

1 Introduction

It's no secret that a significant part behind the long-term success of disruptive innovation relies on the level of awareness it can effectively raise and the overall engagement it is able to create. Designing and executing an effective dissemination and communication strategy, its results and achievements can gain widespread attention and persist far beyond the project's initial run.

Therefore, a solid dissemination and communication strategy should be geared towards ensuring the active involvement of key stakeholders in the project to establish a committed community that can network opportunities for future developments.

1.1 Purpose and scope

The present deliverable (**D4.2 – Final Communication & Dissemination report**), is presented in the framework of EU4CHILD's **WP4 – Community building, Outreach and Exploitation**, specifically within task **T4.2 – Dissemination and Communication**.

This report provides an overview of all key activities and actions related to communication and dissemination that have taken place throughout the project's lifetime. It also gives a quantitative presentation of the performance of our digital channels, participation in physical and online events, publications, online articles... and other details.

The initial strategy for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation was outlined in deliverable **D4.1 – EU4CHILD Impact Master Plan**, submitted in M4 (August 2021). Hence, the contents of this initial plan have been expanded upon and updated accordingly in the present deliverable, which is the project's final report on Communication & Dissemination activities.

2 Dissemination and Communication strategy

Communication activities involve specific measures for promoting the project and the results achieved. The communication plan has the mission to reach out to a broader audience, beyond the core community that composes the pediatric cancer medical field. Similarly, the dissemination plan put in place by EU4CHILD underlines the actions envisioned to build awareness of the project results, creating understanding and aiming for action among the relevant target audience.

The conception and execution of EU4CHILD's overall vision requires promoting the research, findings, outcomes and goals of the project. Thus, the overall objectives set up for the outreach strategy have been defined as follows:

- Increase general awareness and interest about the project to build a solid ecosystem for future dissemination and exploitation of results.
- Establish, maintain and grow a community around EU4CHILD in alignment with the stakeholder management framework.
- Communicate technical, scientific results to specialised target groups and stakeholders.
- Deliver key messages about the project to non-technical target groups and audiences.
- Raise awareness to non-specialised audiences of the added value of EU4CHILD to reach the widest possible community.
- Liaise with other EU, national and international initiatives centered around pediatric cancer to maximize impact.

2.1 Overview on the Communication & Dissemination strategy

As previously outlined in EU4CHILD's Impact Master Plan, outreach activities have been planned in 3 different phases (**Plan & Revisit**, **Early bird communication** and **Targeted communication**), which are closely related to dissemination as well. The common goal was to build and nurture a community and brand around the project, to maximize visibility and engage with end users to foster dialogue and collect feedback on the project's vision and progress.

In this regard, the **timeline** followed has been the following:

- During the first 4 months of the project (**Plan & Revisit** phase) the visual identity and key brand assets of the project have been created, all Communication & Dissemination channels have been set up and the first mapping of stakeholders has been completed.
- From M4 to M6 (**Early bird communication**), the focus progressively shifted towards establishing a recognizable presence in all our digital channels, begin the conversation with related initiatives and start working on additional promotional materials and long-form articles to cover core concepts of the project for a wider audience.

As a general comment, the project's short timeframe (18 months overall) has added an extra layer of complexity to achieving some of these targets with a very tight promotional window. This is most apparent in the number of peer-reviewed publications, which are normally required to undergo an exhaustive submission and approval process that can stretch out for many months. The Covid-19 pandemic has also made an impact in the number and format of many events in these past 2 years.

The fact also remains that building a community from the ground up (especially a virtual one) is a multi-faceted and long journey, which we are proud to have already started and shared with EU4CHILD's sister project, UNICA4EU. This new initiative, which carries on our work for the next year, is an exciting opportunity to reinforce, expand and solidify our communication and dissemination channels going forward.

Type	Indicators	Target	Current
Publications	Scientific and Technical Publications (e.g. peer-reviewed papers, articles, blog posts)	30	1+12
Events	No. events participated	30	5
Webinars	No. workshops/webinars attended	20	6
Webinars	No. workshops/webinars organized	5	6
Website	No. visitors	1,000	878
Printed material	No. hard copies (e.g. flyers) distributed	500	500
Social media	Size of the online community (by the end of the project)	5,000	463
Social media	No. impressions (monthly average)	400	4,176
Videos	No. videos produced	3	13
Newsletters	No. newsletters contributed/released	6	1
Collaboration	No. participants (total) in the fieldwork (survey + interviews/focus groups)	200	235+35

Table 1. KPI tracker for Communication & Dissemination

3 Communication & Dissemination activities implemented

3.1 Visual identity

3.1.1 Logo and brand assets

EU4CHILD's complete visual identity was designed and presented during the first months of the project. This includes the project's **visual guidelines**, **branding assets** (logo variations, icons, banners), **typography** and **color codes** that are shown below.

The blending of caring, symbolized by the **heart**; technology and networks, represented by the **outline of a cube**; and the fight against cancer, depicted by the universally known **ribbon**. **Children** are at the core of EU4CHILD, so the logo remains **playful** in tone, and the **handwritten** font gives it a softer and accessible feel. **Primary colors** – red, yellow and blue – provide brightness and link back to childhood (painting, playing).

Figure 2. EU4CHILD – Main logo

Figure 3. Typography and color codes for EU4CHILD

Figure 4. EU4CHILD – Vertical logo variations

Figure 5. EU4CHILD – Horizontal logo variations

Figure 6. EU4CHILD – Banners

3.1.2 Official templates

As a way of harmonizing all documentation and resources coming from EU4CHILD, several official templates have been produced for the project's deliverables and meeting minutes (Word) and presentations (PowerPoint).

3.2 Online channels

The idea behind EU4CHILD's **Communication & Dissemination toolkit** is to build and maintain a portfolio of all the digital channels and accounts that have been set up for the promotion and uptake of results from the project.

This toolkit includes: the project's official website and social media (Twitter and LinkedIn), together with a dedicated Zenodo repository for Open Access publications.

Figure 7. EU4CHILD's C&D toolkit

3.2.1 Project website

Website	www.eu4child.eu
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The project website is a key element for EU4CHILD's Dissemination and Communication strategy. In fact, it is a hub collating information about the project, its goals and the team behind it. The website has been online from the very beginning of the project and has been designed following EU4CHILD's branding guidelines to nurture and consolidate the project's digital identity.

The structure of the website follows a clear logic, meant to incite interest across all segments of our target audience. It includes the following sections:

- **Home** – our landing page, describing the project, expected results and methodology. It highlights all essential information about EU4CHILD.
- **About** – this page describes the project's vision, goals and work plan in depth.
- **Ecosystem** – this section puts EU4CHILD into context and introduces the opportunities, challenges and risks populating the intersection between AI and pediatric oncology.
- **Advisory Board** – this page contains information on the members of our Advisory Board.
- **Team** – this section offers an overview of the partners behind EU4CHILD.

- **What's new** – this section includes the project's blog, with posts that are updated over time as the project progresses and new material is produced.

**Join us in the creation of an interoperable and distributed
EU ecosystem for action on Pediatric Cancer**

We are designing a new framework for research on Artificial Intelligence (AI), active collaboration and knowledge exchange on two types of childhood cancer:
Neuroblastoma and Nephroblastoma.

Figure 8. EU4CHILD's website - Home page

In terms of performance, the breakdown from the site's metrics on Google Analytics is presented below. This overview spans the project's complete run thus far and shows the aggregated totals. The website has driven a traffic of **3,476 pageviews** and attracted **878 unique users**, of which **15.3% are returning visitors** interested in keeping up to date with the project's overall progress.

Figure 9. Overview of EU4CHILD’s website performance

3.2.2 Social Media

Twitter	@eu4child
LinkedIn	/eu4child

EU4CHILD maintains an active presence on Twitter and LinkedIn, with an aggregated audience of **463 followers** between both platforms. These online channels help to promote new publications and participation in different kinds of events, as they have proven to be the most effective tools when engaging with scientific and healthcare communities.

Figure 10. EU4CHILD – Twitter profile and timeline

Figure 11. EU4CHILD – LinkedIn company page

The project’s **performance overview on social media** is presented below, where significant growth can be observed in the number of followers, impressions and page views for both channels. Once the project’s final deliverables are made available (and especially after the publication of **D2.3 – EU4CHILD’s Roadmap for the successful implementation of the Ecosystem**), they will be promoted and showcased through all our digital channels, which is expected to generate additional traffic to our website.

Followers (total) **463** Impressions (monthly avg) **4.1K** Page views (monthly avg) **1.4K**

Figure 12. Overview of EU4CHILD's social media channels

3.2.2.1 Campaigns

The activities carried out on both Twitter and LinkedIn have been planned according to our social media strategy and editorial calendar. Language, imagery and tone are kept neutral, considering that the topic at hand is sensitive to patients and their families. *Ad hoc* references and keywords were used in all our content. Specific research was conducted to find the top trending hashtags in the field, linking our tweets to other related accounts, allowing us a wider outreach and leveraging the existing audience from their accounts.

Our strategy on social media has followed a mixed recipe combining two different sets of ingredients:

- First, high-level information about the project and the team behind it, packaged into easy-to-digest **general campaigns** that use flashcards and attractive visuals to communicate the main vision, mission and expertise driving EU4CHILD.
- Second, the design and execution of **targeted campaigns** around key milestones (e.g. featured events, meetings or achievements of note, other relevant dates to keep in our editorial calendar).

To further illustrate this, several examples of EU4CHILD's social media campaigns are presented below.

About the Project

This campaign covers everything about the project's vision, mission and methodology to convey our key messages in a straightforward, visually attractive way.

Figure 13. Examples of EU4CHILD's general outreach campaigns – About the project

Partner features

These posts include a short description of one of our partners every week and their main role within EU4CHILD. This is meant to create synergies between EU4CHILD social media channels and our consortium members, growing our audience organically. More about our campaigns and their purpose will be explained in the following sections.

Figure 14. Examples of EU4CHILD's general outreach campaigns – Partner features

Meet the Team

The Meet the Team interviews have been conceived as informal introductions for each partner collaborating in EU4CHILD. All interviews have been recorded and then edited for content generation to share in our website and social media channels. As reference, below are some sample questions used to guide these conversations:

- **Ice breaker:** tell us a bit about your background, occupation and your day-to-day.
- **The project:** EU4CHILD in a nutshell and what is your role in it.
- **The motivation:** your vision for EU4CHILD and the main challenges you see ahead.
- **The highlights:** your takeaway messages and what you envision as the end goal for EU4CHILD.

Interview script
Meet the Team

The Meet the Team interviews are meant to act as informal introductions for each partner collaborating in EU4CHILD. They are intended to take around 30-45 minutes of your time, and will be carried out online through any of the available videoconferencing platforms. Sessions will be recorded and edited for content generation to share in our website and social media channels. As reference, below are some sample questions to guide the conversation.

Ice breaker

- Tell us a little bit about yourself – What is your background and occupation?
- What does your typical weekday look like? Can you walk us through what you do in your day-to-day?

The project

- You are a partner in EU4CHILD. If you had to present our project in the simplest terms possible, what would be the main headline?
- As one of the clinical/technical experts participating in EU4CHILD, how would you define your role in the project?

The motivation

- What was your vision for joining in this initiative? What drew you in initially?
- What are, in your opinion, the most significant roadblocks in our way (i.e. what keeps you up at night about this project)?

The highlights

- One of our goals in EU4CHILD is to bridge the gap between young patients, their caregivers, healthcare professionals and AI experts, in an attempt to bring these communities closer together. If you had to choose, what would you wish each of these groups could take away from our project?
- How do you, personally, define success for this project?

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Meet the Team!
Annelore Hermann

Meet the Team!
Fiona Lyne

Meet the Team!
Angela Mastronuzzi

Figure 15. Examples of EU4CHILD's general outreach campaigns – Meet the Team interviews

News and paper highlights

Additional content regarding the field of pediatric cancer and how it ties into the work of EU4CHILD has also been actively shared, including news and information not just related to our project, but also relevant to the community as a whole (e.g. news of scientific, academic or legal nature from relevant channels across Europe).

Figure 16. Examples of EU4CHILD's general outreach campaigns – News and paper highlights

3.2.3 Zenodo

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/eu4child-pppa>

Following the European Commission guidelines for Open Science, EU4CHILD provides open access to peer-reviewed publications and scientific research data generated within the project, as per our Data Management Plan. There is a dedicated Zenodo community and repository already in place for the project, where all sorts of publications (e.g. slide decks, articles, posters), public deliverables, press releases and more can be found. The repository currently hosts **11 uploads**.

The screenshot displays the Zenodo repository interface for the EU4CHILD project. At the top, the Zenodo logo and navigation options are visible. The main content area is titled 'EU4CHILD project' and features a 'Recent uploads' section with a search bar. Four items are listed, each with a date, version, and 'Open Access' status, along with a 'View' button. The items are: 'EU4CHILD - Roll-up banner' (May 6, 2022), 'EU4CHILD - Fieldwork profiles' (February 15, 2022), 'EU4CHILD - Fieldwork one pager' (February 15, 2022), and 'EU4CHILD - One pager' (February 1, 2022). A sidebar on the right contains a 'New upload' button, the project's logo, and detailed information about the project, including its description as an Open Access Repository, funding by the European Commission, and curation details.

Figure 17. EU4CHILD – Zenodo repository

3.3 Promotional materials

During the project’s run, a series of **promotional material** has been produced and fine-tuned. This effort includes the creation of a project slide deck, a tri-fold brochure, one pagers and a roll-up banner. Additionally, on-going support has been provided for *ad hoc* graphic design, multimedia and other on-demand assets for specific events and promotional actions, which are presented below.

The short duration of the project required that a lot of emphasis be put into the promotional material of various nature, mainly because both awareness about the purpose and the goals of the project are to be disseminated over a short period of time and in the most efficient way possible. The design has been carefully studied to maximize visual appeal. These tools have been living elements that were continuously adapted and refined as the project evolved and matured. Graphical elements are clear, simple and intuitive, and reflect the language used to pursue visibility among the general public as well as experts in the field.

Figure 18. Overview of EU4CHILD's promotional materials

3.3.1 One pager

Meant as a straightforward way of providing a quick, to-the-point overview of the project, EU4CHILD’s one pager is a condensed introduction to our ambition, tools and methodology, making sure to highlight three main questions: *why* what we do is important, *how* we will do it and *what* we are working to achieve. The project’s one pager is available [here](#) at our Zenodo repository.

A crowdsourced Ecosystem to fight Childhood Cancer

We are designing an interoperable **EU framework** for research on Artificial Intelligence (AI), active collaboration and knowledge exchange on Pediatric Cancer

Why Childhood Cancer?

The facts Many paediatric cancers have a genetically distinct component from their adult counterparts, highlighting a need for childhood-specific genomic studies, datasets and therapeutic strategies

Specificity is the mark | Early detection is key | Young survivors deserve better

Our tools

- AI medical imaging
- Natural Language Processing
- Deep Neural Networks

A multidisciplinary roadmap to fight Childhood Cancer

A multi-perspective State-of-the-Art, complemented by a roadmap and guidelines on the mechanisms and tools to implement the ecosystem

Bringing together clinicians, young cancer patients and AI experts

We seek to connect key European stakeholders in Childhood Cancer by means of eXplainable AI to facilitate their interaction and cooperation

A single access point to boost knowledge exchange and collaboration

Our ambition Our one-stop portal will host and curate a EU-wide knowledge base for Childhood Cancer, providing insights on the disease and liaising future opportunities for collaboration

Fostering Open Innovation | Enabling interoperability | Top AI performance and quality | A sound data strategy

Stay in touch! www.eu4child.eu

@eu4child | [in /eu4child](https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu4child) | EU4CHILD receives funding from the European Union's Call for Pilot Projects and Preparatory Actions (PPPA) under Grant Agreement No. 101018783

Figure 19. EU4CHILD – General one pager

3.3.2 Slide deck

The project’s official slide deck serves as one of the entry points for EU4CHILD and conveys an effective and visually attractive introduction to our main vision, the scope, targets and team. EU4CHILD’s slide deck is available through the project’s open access community at Zenodo ([here](#)).

Figure 20. EU4CHILD – Slide deck

3.3.3 Tri-fold brochure

As part of EU4CHILD’s branded merchandise, printed materials like brochures and roll-up banners have been designed and made available in digital format, to be printed out when required (e.g. for display in events and conferences). Physical copies have been handed out at key events. The tri-fold brochure can be found [here](#) at EU4CHILD’s Zenodo repository.

Figure 21. EU4CHILD – Trifold brochure

3.3.4 Roll-up banner

EU4CHILD’s roll-up banner has been designed to announce the presence of the project at in-person events, like IFIC’s 22nd International Conference on Integrated Care at Odense, Denmark. The project’s roll-up banner is available [here](#) at EU4CHILD’s Zenodo repository.

Figure 22. EU4CHILD – Roll-up banner

3.4 Publications

3.4.1 Scientific publications

Type	Title	Authors	Platform
Article	Gaps and Opportunities of Artificial Intelligence Applications for Pediatric Oncology in European Research: A Systematic Review of Reviews and a Bibliometric Analysis	A.E. Tozzi, F. Fabozzi, M. Eckley, I. Croci, V.A. Dell’Anna, E. Colantonio, A. Mastronuzzi	Frontiers in Oncology

Table 2. EU4CHILD – List of peer-reviewed publications

3.4.2 Articles, blog posts and press releases

EU4CHILD’s consortium has also been quite active and enthusiastic in the production of non-scientific publications. In this regard, there is a **dedicated News section** in the project’s website, which currently displays **12 news pieces** ranging from long-form articles, press releases, publications, webinars to general project updates.

Figure 23. A collection of EU4CHILD's awareness publications

3.5 Events, conferences and workshops

Taking into consideration the delicate situation for face-to-face gathering brought forward by the Covid-19 pandemic and the subsequent travel restrictions that have gone into effect, EU4CHILD's partners have made a tremendous effort to participate in several scientific and technical events during these 18 months. Overall, EU4CHILD has been prominently featured in **5 events**, **3 webinars** and **3 workshops**.

Name	Date	Location	Type
Joint workshop with EUStands4PM	21-10-2021	Online	Workshop
Building a community around EU4CHILD	02-12-2021	Online	Workshop
IFIC's 22 nd International Conference on Integrated Care	23-05-2022	Odense (DK)	Conference
AIMed Global Summit	24-05-2022	San Francisco (USA)	Conference
AI Week	24-05-2022	Edmonton (CA)	Conference
SIOP-RTSG Meeting	27-06-2022	Sevilla (ES)	Meeting
Leibniz AI Lab Summer School	27-06-2022	Hannover (DE)	Meeting
EU4CHILD – Paediatric cancer AI framework and knowledge base	27-09-2022	Online	Webinar
EU4CHILD – Community building and policy approach	27-09-2022	Online	Webinar
EU4CHILD – AI for Paediatric Cancer Roadmap for healthcare professionals	28-09-2022	Online	Webinar
EU4CHILD – Value proposition and marketplace	06-10-2022 11-10-2022	Online	Workshop

Table 3. EU4CHILD – List of events

Figure 24. Some featured events (from left to right): Joint workshop with EUStands4PM, IFIC’s 22nd International Conference on Integrated Care, SIOP-RTSG Meeting, EU4CHILD’s webinar on AI for Paediatric Cancer Roadmap for healthcare professionals and insights from EU4CHILD’s value proposition and marketplace workshop

4 Fieldwork overview

4.1 Methodology

As outlined in our **internal fieldwork manual**, EU4CHILD intends to lay the foundations for the development of a multi-purpose AI ecosystem for Childhood Cancer, seeking to understand the main needs and concerns from our stakeholder base. This manual has been prepared to guide the fieldwork efforts of EU4CHILD's team members in their interactions with these key stakeholders (through focus groups, workshops and personal interviews) and to ensure comparability of the end results. For a more detailed overview on our fieldwork methodology and the final analysis of these results, please refer to deliverable **D4.3 – Impact, exploitation and sustainability Final Report**.

4.2 Fieldwork survey

In order to widespread the impact of our fieldwork and complement the work already outlined in our focus groups and interview, a dedicated fieldwork survey was launched through the project's online channels (website and social media).

The survey is available in **3 different languages** ([English](#), [German](#) and [Spanish](#)), is completely **anonymous** and has been carefully crafted to explore how a future platform using AI or other trending technologies could help improve the support given to children and adolescents living with cancer (and survivors), their caregivers and associations that represent them, help improve policy and decision making, and provide researchers and clinicians access to information that will accelerate development of and access to novel diagnostics and therapies for children living with cancer.

Figure 25. Some screenshots from EU4CHILD's online fieldwork survey

Overall, we have received **235 responses** to the fieldwork survey. The dashboard showing the primary data collected from online respondents can be seen below. More in-depth insights are shared in deliverable **D4.3 – Impact, exploitation and sustainability Final Report**, where the complete vision of EU4CHILD's fieldwork efforts and its results is presented and carefully analyzed.

Focusing on this primary data, we can comment on the country, gender, profile and age distributions. In this regard, the online fieldwork survey shows a wide geographical spread, with respondents from **44 countries** worldwide. Top countries in terms of participation are **Spain** (32 responses), **Germany** (26), **Italy** (25), **Ireland** (25), **The Netherlands** (12), **United Kingdom** (12) and **Canada** (10).

The gender distribution shows a **67/33 split** in favor of female respondents. The predominant profile is that of healthcare professionals (130 responses), followed by citizens (32), caregivers (22) and IT experts (16). Age follows an almost normal distribution, where most of the respondents are **between 40 and 60 years old**.

Figure 26. Overview of results from EU4CHILD's fieldwork survey

4.3 Support materials

4.3.1 Fieldwork one pager

In order to introduce the idea behind EU4CHILD's fieldwork, the contents and structure from the general one pager were adapted to reflect a more detailed breakdown of the project's target and the rationale informing our fieldwork methodology. This was meant as a straightforward way of providing a quick, to-the-point overview of the fieldwork, together with a condensed introduction to our value proposition. EU4CHILD's fieldwork one pager is available [here](#) at the project's Zenodo repository.

A crowdsourced Ecosystem to fight Childhood Cancer

EU4CHILD is an EU-funded project with a clear goal: map the current landscape of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications for Childhood Cancer to understand how AI can help improve care pathways in the EU

The facts
Why Childhood Cancer?
 Childhood Cancer represents the leading cause of death from disease for children and adolescents in Europe –accounting for 20% of deaths after infancy– and is a major contributor to morbidity in survivors

Our tools
What is Artificial Intelligence?
 By AI we mean **computer systems** that can perform tasks normally requiring **human intelligence**: visual perception, speech recognition, decision-making, pattern recognition, automatic translation

A complete roadmap to fight Childhood Cancer
 A multidisciplinary **State-of-the-Art and guidelines on priorities** to address and **challenges** to overcome to set up an ecosystem for AI in Childhood Cancer

Bringing together clinicians, young cancer patients and AI experts
 We seek to connect key European stakeholders in Childhood Cancer to facilitate their interaction and cooperation

Our ambition
A single access point to boost knowledge exchange and collaboration
 Our one-stop portal will host and curate a knowledge base for Childhood Cancer, providing insights on the disease and liaising future opportunities for collaboration

Fostering Open Innovation	Enabling interoperability	Top AI performance and quality	A sound data strategy
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Stay in touch! www.eu4child.eu

 @eu4child
 /eu4child
 EU4CHILD receives funding from the European Union's Call for Pilot Projects and Preparatory Actions (PPPA) under Grant Agreement No. 101018783

Figure 27. EU4CHILD – Fieldwork one pager

4.3.2 Stakeholder profiles

To address the multi-disciplinarity of our fieldwork interviews and focus groups, **6 personalized profiles** (for Caregivers, Children-Adolescents, Healthcare professionals, Healthcare providers, IT companies, Policy Makers) have been created to cater to each type of stakeholder's needs and expectations. All stakeholder profiles are available [here](#) at EU4CHILD's Zenodo repository.

A crowdsourced Ecosystem to fight Childhood Cancer

For survivors, children and adolescents living with cancer

Welcome to EU4CHILD!
We are setting up focus groups with key people –like you– to understand their needs and views on the usefulness of a potential AI-based platform for Childhood Cancer. In these sessions, we aim to identify ongoing topics and potential barriers in the uptake of AI solutions for the diagnosis, prognosis, treatment and care of Childhood Cancer.

Our focus groups

Join us for a conversation on...

- Information sources & digital skills
- The patient journey in pediatric cancer
- The potential of AI in pediatric cancer
- The platform itself: key features & services

From 6 to 15 participants

Sessions will be recorded

1 hour per session

What value does EU4CHILD bring to this conversation?

- Reinforcing the importance of specialized care
- Advocating for trust, transparency & explainability in AI
- Protecting & guaranteeing patients' fundamental rights

Our privacy policy

What about my data?

In compliance with the GDPR, all information you share with us shall be treated confidentially and will not be shared with any party outside of EU4CHILD's consortium. As a participant, your profile will be anonymized and no indication of your identity shall be disclosed unless with your express consent. For further details, please refer to our [Informed Consent Form](#).

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Figure 28. Example of a fieldwork profile for survivors, children and adolescents living with cancer

4.3.3 Information and consent forms

A fundamental part of our process for involving stakeholder in these fieldwork research activities (e.g. personal interviews, workshops and surveys) is to secure their informed consent.

In this sense, a very straightforward template was produced to clearly communicate how stakeholders' data and opinions will be stored, archived, shared internally among EU4CHILD's consortium members and analyzed for internal purposes only. Fieldwork data has been

adequately anonymized, in order to preserve stakeholders’ privacy and always in compliance with the GDPR.

Informed Consent Document Template and Guidelines
Informed Consent Form

Project title EU4CHILD – European foundations for CHILDhood Cancer Ecosystem
Organization Please include the contact information for your organization
Contact person Please specify the name of your main contact
Contact email Please specify the email of your main contact
Participant ID
Date

We are delighted to invite you to take part in EU4CHILD activities. EU4CHILD is designing a new framework for research on Artificial Intelligence (AI), active collaboration and knowledge exchange on childhood cancer. This ecosystem will be able to provide decision support and treatment recommendations for health and care professionals, researchers and policy makers, with the help of AI. For patients and their families, the ecosystem is intended to provide better understanding of the disease and treatment.

You are being offered the opportunity to take part in this research study because your profile matches those of the key stakeholders for our project, and your input is extremely valuable for us to better understand your needs. From all this information we gather, several documents will be produced in order to share our conclusions with the EU Commission.

You will be offered to participate in research activities such as personal interviews, workshops and surveys. Your data and opinions will be stored, archived, shared internally among EU4CHILD consortium members and analyzed for internal purposes only and we will not share them with any other external partner at any point. Your data will be anonymized, in order to preserve your privacy, always in compliance with the GDPR with regard to the processing of your data. Please, bear in mind that no monetary compensation is planned for your participation in these activities.

You can pose questions and exert your rights to be informed, access, rectification, erasure, to restrict the processing, object, or any other under EU legislation, by contacting EU4CHILD's contact for exerting these rights. By signing this consent form, you indicate that you are voluntarily choosing to take part in this research. You will receive a copy of the signed and dated form to keep for future reference.

Full name of participant (and representative) Please fill in
Date Please fill in
Place Please fill in

Signature of the participant or the participant's legally authorized representative

This project has received funding from the European Union's Call for Pilot Projects and Preparatory Actions (PPPA) under Grant Agreement No. 101018783 © EU4CHILD 2021-2022

Figure 29. Informed consent for EU4CHILD's fieldwork

5 Conclusions

This deliverable is presented primarily as the final update on EU4CHILD's Dissemination and Communication strategy and the current state-of-play after the project's 18 months of operation.

In this regard, several major milestones were accomplished: the project's visual identity and key branding assets have been produced, main digital channels for the project have been set up and consolidated, and several joint efforts on the publication and promotional fronts have successfully come into fruition.

As a consequence, EU4CHILD displays a harmonized, easily recognizable brand identity to rely on, which has in turn allowed us to build a solid online presence and maintain regular interactions with a tight-knit, growing community around AI and its wider ramifications in pediatric oncology and ultimately, the healthcare realm.

As a living creature, EU4CHILD's Communication and Dissemination strategy has required a collaborative, dynamic and constant effort from the consortium and as such, has also evolved in parallel with the project itself. Ultimately, this means that all **outreach materials, channels and tools** described in this document have been carefully revised and fine-tuned to adequately reflect the project's journey and its accomplishments.

Naturally, as the project went on and progressively reached a higher degree of maturity, emphasis has shifted in favor of **more targeted dissemination (scientific) activities**. As a consequence, **fieldwork and networking efforts** have intensified in this last stage, leveraging on the unique opportunity put forward by our digital channels to maximize the project's reach and visibility.

Furthermore, these efforts have also fed into the work devoted to drafting a tailored **fieldwork and value proposition** for EU4CHILD, which is further explored in deliverable **D4.3 – Impact, exploitation and sustainability Final Report**.

All in all, this is not the end of the road for EU4CHILD's outreach plans, but just the first chapter in a story that will carry on with our sister project, UNICA4EU. During this last transitional period (July-October), there has been a joint effort from both consortiums to align our visions on these two initiatives. From a communication and dissemination perspective, this means providing UNICA4EU with the necessary information and resources to build on EU4CHILD's achievements and already consolidated tools (e.g. our virtual community and fieldwork results) to further expand our online and physical presence through a wider network and new, exciting opportunities for collaboration in the coming year.

